

ACTION OF SODIUM ON ETHYL β -METHYLBUTANE- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -TRICARBOXYLATE. PART III. A SYNTHESIS OF *cis*-ALLOSANTENIC ACID

By RAM NARAYAN CHAKRAVARTI

In a previous paper it has been shown that the product of sodium condensation of ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate on methylation followed by hydrolysis of the resulting product furnishes β -methylpentane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid. The isomeric acid, γ -methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid, m.p. 178° , has now been synthesised in a state of purity following the general method outlined in Part II. The triethyl ester of the latter has been cyclised, hydrolysed and esterified to give ethyl 2:3-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylate. This readily reacts with hydrogen cyanide and the cyanohydrin on dehydration, hydrolysis and reduction yields *cis*-allosantenic acid, m.p. $151-52^\circ$. The stereochemical configurations of the isomeric santenic acids cannot be regarded as definitely established.

In Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 173) it has been shown that the product obtained by the action of sodium on ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate on treatment with methyl iodide furnished chiefly ethyl 3:5-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate (I), since on hydrolysis the latter yielded β -methylpentane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$), m.p. $178-79^\circ$. The present paper deals with the synthesis and reactions of the isomeric γ -methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) which might have been formed if the condensation product had the alternative structure (II).

(I)

(II)

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -methylbutane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (IV, $R=H$) (Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 425) on treatment with sodium ethoxide and methyl iodide under the conditions described in the experimental part affords ethyl $\gamma\delta$ -dicyano- γ -methylpentane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (IV, $R=Me$). This on hydrolysis furnishes γ -methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$), m.p. 178° , in an excellent yield. Sen-gupta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 343), who prepared this acid by a different method, does not seem to have obtained it in a state of purity. The corresponding triethyl ester on treatment with sodium followed by hydrolysis of the resulting product gives 2:3-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic acid (V) as a liquid which has been characterised by the formation of a semicarbazone, m.p. 204° .

The ethyl ester of the keto-acid (V) readily reacts with hydrogen cyanide and the cyanohydrin is dehydrated with phosphoryl chloride and pyridine and the resulting product hydrolysed to give an unsaturated dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 140-45° which probably consists of a mixture of (VI) and (VII). The mixture of unsaturated acids on catalytic hydrogenation in presence of Adam's platinum oxide catalyst affords 2:3-dimethylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid. Treatment of this acid with acetyl chloride furnishes an anhydride, m.p. 92°, along with a non-separable mixture of isomeric santenic acids (*cf.* Komppa and Rohrmann, *Ber.*, 1934, 67 B, 828). The anhydride on hydrolysis with alcoholic potash gives an acid, m.p. 151-52°.

Obviously, 2:3-dimethylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid should be capable of existence in two *cis*-forms (VIII) and (IX) and two *trans*-forms (X) and (XI).

(VIII)

(X)

(IX)

(XI)

One of the *cis*-acids, m.p. 171° (anhydride, m.p. 113-14°) was isolated by Aschan by the oxidation of natural santenol or santenone and was designated as santenic acid. Another *cis*-acid, m.p. 151-52° (anhydride, m.p. 92°) was prepared synthetically by Enkvist (*Finska Kem. Medd.*, 1932, 41, 74, 85; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1933, ii, 137, 261) and Komppa (*Ber.*, 1932, 66 B, 1708), and by Komppa and Rohrmann (*loc. cit.*) using a modification of the Komppa synthesis of camphoric acid. The acid was called allosantenic acid by Enkvist (*loc. cit.*). There can be little doubt that the cyclopentane acid described above is identical with *cis*-allosantenic acid. This, therefore, constitutes an independent synthesis of this interesting acid.

Enkvist (*loc. cit.*) who has studied the stereochemistry of the santenic acids, also succeeded in converting santenic acid and allosantenic acid into their respective *trans*-modifications, m.p. 166-67° and 129-30°; following the universal method of Aschan (*Annalen*, 1912, 387, 56). According to him *cis*-allosantenic acid should be best represented by (IX) as it yields an anhydride more readily than does the *cis*-santenic acid which should, therefore, be (VIII). The evidence regarding the stereochemical configurations of the isomeric santenic acids is not, however, quite conclusive, since camphoric acid in which one of the *gem*-dimethyl groupings is situated on the same side of the two carboxyl groups (as in VIII) readily furnishes an anhydride. Moreover, the conversion of santenic acid to allosantenic acid which doubtless proceeds through the *trans*-monobromosantenic acid and the related unsaturated acid, santenenic acid (*cf.* Aschan, "Öfversigt af Finska Vetenskaps-societetens Förhandlingar", 53A, Nr. 8, 1910) is explained on the basis of formula (XI) which according to Enkvist should in reality represent *trans*-allosantenic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl γδ-Dicyano-γ-methylpentane-αδ-dicarboxylate (IV, R=Me).—Ethyl *αβ*-dicyano-*β*-methylbutane-*αδ*-dicarboxylate was prepared by condensing ethyl laevulate with ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of acetamide and glacial acetic acid and allowing the product obtained to react with

hydrocyanic acid (*cf.* Banerjee, *loc. cit.*). The dicyano-ester (18.7 g.) was added to an ice-cold solution of sodium (1.62 g.) in absolute ethyl alcohol (27 c.c.). Methyl iodide (5 c.c.) was then added to it and it was kept overnight. The next day, it was refluxed on the water-bath for 12 hours with the addition of a little methyl iodide from time to time. When cold the product was treated with water and the oil separating was taken up in ether and washed with dilute potassium hydroxide solution to remove traces of iodine. The ether was then evaporated and the residual oil distilled in *vacuo* when ethyl $\gamma\delta$ -dicyano- γ -methylpentane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (IV, R=Me) was obtained as a colourless mobile liquid boiling at 185°/5mm., yield 18 g. (Found : C, 59.6; H, 7.0. $C_{14}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires C, 60.0; H, 7.1 per cent).

γ -Methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (III, $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The methylated product (17.5 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing on a sand-bath for 16-18 hours with 90 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The clear solution, thus obtained, was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and the dry mass extracted with ether. On evaporation of the ether about 13 g. of a partially solid product were obtained. It was dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3 c.c.) and heated to 110° for 6 hours, a current of hot alcohol vapour being passed through the liquid. The product was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water. The ether was then evaporated and the liquid remaining distilled in *vacuo* when ethyl γ -methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylate was obtained as a colourless liquid boiling at 154°/5mm., yield 13 g. (Found : C, 59.6; H, 8.6. $C_{18}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 59.6; H, 8.6 per cent).

The tricarboxylic ester (2 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) till a clear solution was obtained. It was then evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and crystallised several times from concentrated hydrochloric acid when pure γ -methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) was obtained in colourless crystals, m. p. 178°. (Found : C, 59.2; H, 8.5. $C_8H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 49.5; H, 6.4 per cent).

Ethyl 2:3-Dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate.—The tricarboxylic ester (7.5 g.) was heated on the water-bath with molecular sodium (0.69 g.) suspended in dry benzene (18 c.c.). Vigorous evolution of hydrogen started on heating and the reaction was complete in 45 minutes. It was then treated with ice-water, and acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated, washed well with water and the benzene evaporated completely under reduced pressure. The liquid obtained was then distilled in *vacuo*, b.p. 135°/5mm., yield 4.8 g. It gave a dark violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 60.6; H, 7.6. $C_{18}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 60.9; H, 7.8 per cent).

2:3-Dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic Acid (V).—The above condensation product (4.5 g.) was hydrolysed by heating on a sand-bath for 6 hours with 50 c.c. of 6% hydrochloric acid. The clear solution, thus obtained, was neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter present. The aqueous solution was then acidified with hydrochloric acid, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. Crude 2:3-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic acid (V) (2.8 g.) was obtained as a liquid. The *semicarbazone* crystallises from water and decomposes at 204°. (Found : C, 50.3; H, 6.9. $C_8H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires C, 50.7; H, 7.0 per cent).

Ethyl 2:3-Dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylate.—The keto-acid (8 g.) was esterified with absolute alcohol (40 c.c.) and 4 c.c. of alcoholic hydrogen chloride (saturated at 0°), by heating on the water-bath for 8-10 hours. The alcohol was then distilled off and the residue taken up in ether. It was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water, dried over

anhydrous calcium chloride and the solvent evaporated. The oil remaining was then distilled at $99^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$, yield 8.2 g. (Found : C, 65.0; H, 8.7. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7 per cent).

Action of Anhydrous Hydrocyanic acid on the Keto-ester (V).—The above keto-ester (5g.) was added to cold anhydrous liquid hydrocyanic acid prepared from powdered potassium cyanide (10g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) diluted with an equal volume of water. The condensation was brought about in presence of a drop of potassium cyanide solution. It was kept overnight at 0° and the cyanohydrin formed was stabilised by adding a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid. Excess of hydrocyanic acid was evaporated off completely at the pump, when the crude cyanohydrin of the keto-ester was obtained.

Dehydration of the Cyanohydrin and its Ultimate Hydrolysis: Formation of a mixture of Santenenic and isoSantenenic Acids.—The crude cyanohydrin obtained above was heated with phosphorus oxychloride (23 c.c.) and dry pyridine (85 c.c.) at $145\text{--}50^{\circ}$ for 1 hour. It was then cooled in ice and carefully decomposed with ice-water. The product was acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted repeatedly with ether. The oil obtained on evaporation of the ether was hydrolysed by heating on a sand-bath for 24 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.). When cold the solid insoluble product (2.5 g.) was filtered off. The crude acid melted at $130\text{--}40^{\circ}$ and even after repeated crystallisations melted at $140\text{--}45^{\circ}$ and was a mixture of santenenic and isosantenenic acids. (Found : C, 58.5; H, 6.5. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 58.7; H, 6.5 per cent).

cis-Allosantenenic Acid (IX).—The above mixture of unsaturated acids (1.01 g.) was dissolved in pure glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and shaken with platinum oxide (0.1 g.) in an atmosphere of pure hydrogen under atmospheric pressure and at the room temperature (28°). For the first 10 minutes the absorption was quite rapid, during which time 90 c.c. of hydrogen were absorbed and then the rate suddenly dropped to a very slow but constant value, and for the absorption of the remaining 70 c.c. of hydrogen it took 3 hours. After the absorption was complete it was filtered off and the acetic acid solution was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The dry acid (0.85 g.) was treated with acetyl chloride (2 c.c.) and kept overnight. It was then kept in an evacuated desiccator over potassium hydroxide. The liquid residue, thus obtained, was taken up in ether and extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution to remove acidic impurities. On evaporation of the ether *cis*-allosantenenic anhydride was obtained as a crystalline solid. It crystallises readily from petroleum ether in slender needles, m.p. 92° . (Found : C, 64.1; H, 7.1. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 64.2; H, 7.1 per cent).

The sodium carbonate extract on acidification gave a mixture of isomeric santenic acids which could not be separated.

The pure *cis*-allosantenenic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the anhydride with alcoholic potash. It crystallises from water, m.p. $151\text{--}52^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 57.7; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 58.0; H, 7.5 per cent).

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